

OBSERVATIONS ON THE EGG-SACS OF FOUR *PALYSTES* SPP. IN THE FERNKLOOF NATURE RESERVE (ARANEAE: SPARASSIDAE)

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ABSTRACT

The egg-sacs made by four *Palystes* species in the Fernkloof Nature Reserve, Hermanus, Western Cape are discussed. In *Palystes castaneus* Latreille, 1819, *P. leppanae* Pocock, 1902 and *P. superciliosus* L. Koch, 1875, the typical fist-sized sac envelopes of tough, papery silk reinforced with leaves, twigs and other debris were observed. This is the first time report for *P. leppanae*. The females remain in the vicinity of the egg-sac, usually on top of it, until the spiderlings emerge. Of special interest was the egg sac retreat of *Palystes kreuzmanni* Jäger & Kunz 2010, a fynbos species, that deposit the egg sac between the leaves of plants and for the first time the female was found enclosing herself with the eggs in the same retreat.

Key words: SANSa, distribution, Western Cape, Fynbos

INTRODUCTION

As part of the South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) biodiversity surveys are undertaken in the Western Cape Province. Fernkloof Nature Reserve (FNR), a fynbos reserve in the Western Cape, that covers 1800 ha in the Kleinrivier Mountains above Hermanus is being surveyed. Six of the seven endemic South African plant families are found in the FNR and it represents an exceptionally high plant diversity with representatives of over 1600 species of the Cape Floral Kingdom.

The aim of this survey is to compile the first checklist of the spider species of the FNR. Surveys in the FNR are still underway and to date 99 genera and 137 spider species have been sampled (Hamilton-Attwell 2018 a,b). During the surveys the egg sac retreats made by four *Palystes* species namely *Palystes castaneus* Latreille, 1819, *P. leppanae* Pocock, 1902, *P. superciliosus* L. Koch, 1875 and *P. kreuzmanni* Jäger & Kunz 2010 were observed. Of special interest was the egg sac retreat of *P. kreuzmanni*, an endemic fynbos species.

METHODS

During regular visits in 2018 and 2019 to FNR four *Palystes* species were recorded and photographed. The plant species that *P. kreuzmanni* was found on, were identified and images were taken. Voucher specimens are housed in the National Collection of Arachnida (NCA) at the Agricultural Research Institute (ARC) in Pretoria.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Fourteen *Palystes* species are known from South Africa (World Spider Catalogue 2020). *Palystes* species are nocturnal hunting spiders and during the day, they are inactive and usually found on vegetation. Little is still known about their egg sacs except for that of *P. castaneus* and *P. superciliosus* (Croeser 1979, 1996; Warren 1926).

The egg sac is a fist-sized nest enclosed by tough, papery silk reinforced with leaves, twigs and other debris (Fig. 1). The young *P. superciliosus* hatch some 17 days after the eggs have been laid (Warren 1926) and work their way through the walls of the egg sac about 4 days later (Fig. 2)

Figure 1. *Palystes superciliosus* egg sac.

Figure 2. *Palystes superciliosus* egg sac with emerging spiderlings.

Palystes castaneus, Latreille, 1819

Palystes castaneus is a southern African endemic species described by Latreille (1819) with type locality only given as "Cape of Good Hope". The species is presently recorded from Mozambique, Zimbabwe and South Africa. In South Africa it is known from three provinces (Free State, Northern Cape and Western Cape) including several protected areas (Fig. 3).

Due to its wide geographical range in Southern Africa the species is listed as Least Concern. This is the first record of the species from FNR.

For field identification the uniform dark sternum and venter part of the abdomen is one of the diagnostic characters of *P. castaneus* (Fig. 4).

The egg sac is a fist-sized nest enclosed by tough, papery silk reinforced with leaves, twigs and other debris. It is attached to the vegetation with the female in close proximity (Fig. 5).

Figure 3. Map showing the distribution of *Palystes Castaneus*.

Figure 4. Female *Palystes castaneus* ventral view. Photo credit Y. Klein.

Figure 5. Female *Palystes castaneus* on egg sac.

***Palystes leppanae* Pocock, 1902**

This is a South African endemic described by Pocock (1902) from Grahamstown. The species are mainly known from the Eastern Provinces but it is now for the first time reported from FNR in the Western Cape (Fig. 6). Due to its wide geographic range the species is listed as Least Concern.

For field identification the abdomen is mottled greyish brown with heart mark outlined; flanked by series of paler spots; venter dark crescent mark posterior to epigastric groove followed by rich reddish brown background decorated with numerous white spots (Fig. 7). The egg sac is large enclosing the egg cocoon and leaves in a dense silk nest (Fig. 8).

Figure 6. Map showing the distribution of *Palystes leppanae*.

Figure 7. Female *P. leppanae* dorsal view. Photo credit Linda Wiese

Figure 8. Female *Palystes leppanae* on egg sac.

***Palystes superciliosus* L. Koch, 1875**

A southern African species described by L. Koch (1875) with type locality only given as “Südafrika”. It is known from Mozambique, Namibia, Swaziland and South Africa. The species has a very wide distribution throughout South Africa and is known from all the provinces and occurs in more than 10 protected areas (Fig. 9). Due to its wide geographical range, the species is listed as Least Concern.

Figure 9. Map showing the distribution of *Palystes superciliosus*.

In *P. superciliosus* males and females have a range of markings varying from the nearly uniformly pale brown abdomen to specimens of both sexes with an undulating longitudinal dark chocolate line laterally, subtended by a broader white to creamy yellow band. Abdomen ventrally without markings except for 4 longitudinal striations between spinnerets and dark transverse bar immediately posterior to epigastric groove. Sternum with single dark transverse bar between coxae II. Anterolateral face of coxae dark.

Figure 10. Female *Palystes superciliosus*.

Figure 11. Female *P. superciliosus* on egg sac.

Warren (1926) studied the egg sac of *P. superciliosus* and found they make more than one sac. He estimated that a female laid approximately 800 eggs during an 18-24 month life span.

***Palystes kreuzmanni* Jäger & Kunz, 2010**

Palystes kreuzmanni was described by Jäger & Kunz (2010) and is presently known only from four localities in the Western Cape (Kleinmond, Pringle Bay, Du Toitskloof and FNR) (Fig. 12). Due to the species having a small restricted distribution range (<5 000 km²), it is listed as Endangered.

P. kreuzmanni differs from other species in the dark reddish brown to black sternum, without any bands; the leg coxae is without black bands; ventral abdomen with red patch between epigastric furrow and spinnerets becoming blackish anterior and posterior and including one pair of small white patches in the middle and four longitudinal lines of tiny muscle sigillae; further bright dots situated laterally of the red patch.

The type specimens of *P. kreuzmanni* were sampled in May 2004 from silk retreats made between apical leaves of a *Leucadendron* sp. (Fig. 14) (Jäger & Kunz, 2010).

Figure 12. Map showing the distribution of *Palystes kreuzmanni*

The first specimen of *P. kreuzmanni* from the FNR was sampled during April 2018. It was collected in the top 4-6 leaves of *Othonna quinquedentata* (Asteraceae) (Fig. 15). The female was enclosed in the retreat. When the tip was cut-off (handled), she shot out through the opening of the nest. In the egg-sac retreat several young spiderlings and exoskeletons were present.

Figure 15 a. *Othonna quinquedentata* top 4-6 leaves on stem before florescence develops. b: Opening on top of nest in *O. quinquedentata* c: *O. quinquedentata* plant with florescence and flowers.

In June 2019 the second *P. kreuzmanni* was sampled from spindle-shaped nests made in the leaves of *Leucodendron salignum* (tolbosse) (Figs 16) as also reported by Jäger & Kuntz (2010). There were several nests but only two were sampled. On closer inspection, it was found that the one retreat contained a number of small and medium sized spiderlings, frass and exoskeletons.

Figure 16 a: *Leucodendron salignum* (female) b: Male plant c: Tips of branches of *L. salignum* with retreats.

Figure 13. Female *P. kreuzmanni* ventral view

Figure 14 *Leucadendron* sp. from where *P. kreuzmanni* was sampled.

The second retreat appeared to harbour two objects that turn out to be a female with an egg-sac (Fig. 17). When the nests were opened it became clear that the one nest is older than the other. In the old nest different sized spiderlings, exoskeletons and frass were observed as well as remnants of the old egg-sac and possibly eggs that did not hatch, were visible (Fig. 18).

Figure 17 Young retreat between leaves of *L. salignum* with egg-sac and female, *P. kreutzmanni* protecting the eggs.

Figure 18 Comparison of a young nest and an older egg sac with only dead eggs some frass and skeletons. nests

What is interesting is that during the process of opening the younger nest, the spider, did not move or get agitated (Fig. 17). In the opened nest the second structure observed during the initial examination, was an egg-sac with 46 fresh eggs. No embryos were yet visible in the eggs (Fig. 18).

CONCLUSION

The egg sac and mother care behaviour of *P. castaneus*, *P. superciliosus*, *P. leppanae* is completely different from *P. kreutzmanni*. In the first three species the egg sacs are made and then covered with a layer of silk and leaves. This covered large sac is suspended among vegetation. The female usually positioned herself on the egg sac and is aggressive while protecting it. In *P. kreutzmanni* the female make the egg sac, among the leaves of a plant then covering it with layers of silk and tightening the surrounding leaves around the retreat with silk. The female stays with the eggs in the retreat.

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NOTE FROM THE EDITOR

Other records of *Palystes* egg sacs is that of *Palystes perornatus* from the Vernon Crooke Nature Reserve where female sit on egg sac.

Palystes perornatus female Photo credit D. Herbert